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Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)

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The Editor-in-Chief

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Death Anxiety, Religiosity, and Meaning in Life as Predictors of Relapse among Psychiatric Patients in selected Neuro-Psychiatric Hospitals in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the predictive roles of death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning in life on relapse among psychiatric patients. Data were collected from 86 participants from Ekiti State Teaching Hospital in Ado-Ekiti and the Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The hypothesis was analysed using binary logisitcs with the aid of IBM-SPSS. Logistic Regression results showed that death anxiety dimensions significantly predicted relapse, $\chi^2(5) = 18.11$, $p = .003$, explaining 19–29% of the variance, with fear of death emerging as a significant negative predictor (OR = .86, $p = .01$). Religiosity dimensions were not significant overall, $\chi^2(2) = 5.53$, $p = .06$, although extrinsic religiosity contributed marginally (OR = 1.09, $p = .04$). Meaning in life alone did not predict relapse, $\chi^2(1) = 1.23$, $p = .27$. However, when all predictors were combined, the model was significant, $\chi^2(8) = 26.40$, $p = .001$. In the full model, fear of death (OR = .87, $p = .01$), neutral acceptance (OR = 1.19, $p = .02$), and intrinsic religiosity (OR = .88, $p = .04$) uniquely predicted relapse. The study concluded that lower fear of death and stronger intrinsic religiosity may reduce relapse likelihood among psychiatric patients.

Keywords: Religiosity, Death Anxiety, Meaning in life, Relapse, Psychiatric patients.

Introduction

Mental health conditions account for a significant share of the global disease burden, and recurring episodes remain one of the major obstacles to sustained recovery and effective rehabilitation efforts (WHO, 2010). Although a variety of therapeutic interventions exist, many individuals continue to experience repeated episodes of illness. In the case of mental health disorders, evidence from several studies shows that the proportion of patients who relapse is extremely high, with estimates ranging from about 50% to over 90% (Armstrong, 2018). Mental health disorders place considerable emotional, social, and financial strain on affected individuals as well as on the families who support them (Izibeloko & Amiengheme, 2012). Most mental health conditions respond well to appropriate treatment; however, many patients still experience repeated episodes. When a mental health disorder relapse occurs, it often leads to repeated hospital admissions and negatively affects long-term clinical outcomes. These recurrent admissions also carry substantial financial implications, as hospitalization alone can account for approximately one-half to two-thirds of the total cost of managing a person living with schizophrenia (Munirat et al., 2018). Relapse and frequent hospital admissions are common among individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, placing a significant strain on those living with these conditions (Ayano, 2017). According to Schennachj et al. (2012), relapse refer to as a worsening of psychopathological symptoms or re-hospitalization in the year after hospital discharge. More broadly, relapse denotes the re-emergence of a disease or health condition after a period of remission or noticeable improvement (Oyedele et al., 2021). In the context of mental health conditions, relapse describes the reappearance of symptoms following a phase of recovery or noticeable improvement (Chaurotia et al, 2016). Relapses may also lead the patients to stay on medication for a longer period (Varie et al., 2012).

Relapse can emerge at virtually any point in the treatment process. It may occur immediately after a patient returns home, during a trial discharge, at the point of admission, or even after a period of abstaining from substance use and attempting to maintain a stable routine. Research has highlighted several determinants of relapse, among which poor adherence to prescribed medication and neglect of established relapse-prevention measures are prominent contributors (Kabisa et al., 2021). Relapse in individuals with psychiatric disorders represents a major challenge in mental health care, undermining personal recovery, placing additional strain on families, and exerting pressure on healthcare resources. Gaining insight into the frequency and

contributing factors of relapse is essential for designing effective prevention and management approaches. Such recurrences are commonly linked to poorer clinical outcomes, including heightened symptom severity, diminished quality of life, and lasting impairments in daily functioning (Chakrabarti, 2014). Despite substantial progress in treatment modalities, relapse rates remain persistently high (World Health Organization [WHO], 2005), imposing considerable emotional, social, and economic burdens. The morbidity and economic cost of psychiatric disorders, particularly depression, now rival or exceed those of chronic physical conditions such as AIDS, cancer, and coronary heart disease (Cooper, 2003; Scott et al., 2003). Moreover, inadequate community care and suboptimal treatment adherence continue to exacerbate relapse and re-hospitalization rates (Loaner, 1997; Knott, 1997). While previous studies (Oyedele et al., 2021; Olara, 2023; Birhan et al., 2025) have largely focused on biomedical and pharmacological determinants, limited research has examined psychological factors on relapse among psychiatric patients. This study, therefore, investigates death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning in life as predictors of relapse among psychiatric patients.

Religiosity has attracted growing interest in academic research, its influence on mental health care continues to be relatively under-investigated (Friedli, 2000). Earlier research has indicated that religious beliefs can play a substantial role in shaping individuals' help-seeking behaviours and adherence to prescribed treatments (Chadda, Agarwal, Singh, & Raheja, 2001; Loewenthal, 2012). For instance, higher levels of religious observance have been linked to delays in seeking mental health services (Bilu & Witztum, 1993; Greenberg, 1992). Consequently, religiosity is defined as an individual's commitment to religious beliefs and practices (Saffari, Chen, & Pakpour, 2019). While religion refers to an organized system of beliefs, rituals, and moral codes focused on the divine, religiosity reflects the personal level of participation, devotion, and internalization within that system (Robinson-Edwards & Kewley, 2018). This construct is multidimensional; behavioral, cognitive, and affective and inherently complex to conceptualize (Kilbourne, Cummings, & Levine, 2009). Empirical evidence indicates that religiosity may influence health management, including self-care practices, mental well-being, and perceived social support (Permana, 2018; Yuniarti, Dewi, Ningrum, & Widiastuti, 2013).

Recent evidence done by Aggarwal et al. (2023) found that spiritual well-being correlates with lower depressive and anxiety symptoms, whereas negative religious coping correlates with worse outcomes. Malinakova et al. (2024) demonstrated that under conditions of high sensory-processing sensitivity, religiosity/spirituality can associate with greater mental-health

symptoms. Boateng et al. (2023) found that in some U.S. samples, higher religiosity was associated with greater utilisation of mental-health services, challenging earlier assumptions of uniform reluctance. Qualitative work by Antoniou and Kalogeropoulos (2024) further revealed that for religious client's faith can serve as both resilience and barrier depending on context and community attitudes. Collectively, these studies suggest religiosity may function both as a coping resource and a structural barrier to professional mental-health care, depending on individual interpretation of faith, religious culture, stigma, and help-seeking attitudes.

Death anxiety is a universal psychological experience that transcends cultural and religious boundaries. It represents a multidimensional construct involving emotional, cognitive, and existential concerns related to mortality (Alkozei et al., 2019). The inevitability of death evokes fear and uncertainty, often influenced by individual factors such as religiosity, gender, age, and psychological state (Chan & Yap, 2009; Dadfar & Lester, 2020; Lehto & Stein, 2009). Although widely discussed, death anxiety remains theoretically complex, and alleviating it is considered essential for improving overall well-being (Zhang et al., 2019). Empirical studies have associated death anxiety with a range of mental health conditions, such as anxiety disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, depression, and eating disorders (Iverach et al., 2014; Menzies & Dar-Nimrod, 2017; Ongider & Eyuboglu, 2013). High levels of death anxiety have been found to contribute to increased psychological distress and a diminished quality of life (Galek et al., 2007; Willis et al., 2019). Recent research indicates that death anxiety may serve as a transdiagnostic factor, playing a role in emotional dysregulation and the experience of existential distress (Menzies et al., 2019).

Meaning in life refers to an individual's ability to make sense of life experiences, set personal goals, and view life as purposeful and valuable (Martela & Steger, 2016). It encompasses two key dimensions: the presence of meaning, which reflects a sense of coherence and purpose, and the search for meaning, representing the active pursuit of significance and direction in life (Steger et al., 2006). Research indicates that negative beliefs about the self, the world, and the future are predictive of depressive symptoms, highlighting the critical role of personal meaning in supporting psychological well-being (Dulaney et al., 2018). Empirical research indicates that greater perceived meaning in life is linked to reduced symptoms of depression and anxiety, as well as better recovery outcomes in both clinical and non-clinical populations (Abernethy et al., 2024; Behav. Sci., 2024). Consequently, meaning in life acts as a protective factor that fosters resilience and psychological adaptation, underscoring its importance in understanding

relapses among individuals with psychiatric conditions. Based on the empirical evidences, the study hypothesized that:

1. Death anxiety will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients.
2. Religiosity will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients.
3. Meaning in life will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients.
4. Death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning in life will jointly predict relapse among psychiatric patients.

Method

Research Design

The ex-post facto research design was adopted in this study. This is because the researcher does not have total control over the variables of interest. The independent variables in the study are death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning in Life while the dependent variable is relapse.

Research Setting

This research was carried out at the Ekiti State Teaching Hospital in Ado Ekiti and the Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. These facilities provide both inpatient and outpatient mental health services and were suitable for the study because they serve patients with a wide range of psychiatric diagnoses and relapse histories. This setting offers a realistic environment to explore how religiosity, death anxiety, and meaning in life influence relapse. Additionally, the hospital's diverse, multicultural, and multi-faith population enabled a meaningful investigation into how religious orientation and existential beliefs impact psychological adjustment and recovery in psychiatric patients.

Study Sample

Eighty-six (86) participants were involved in this study. This includes psychiatric patients (inpatients and outpatients), they also include 50 males and 36 females and the participants were between the age of 18 and 55 years who are either of Christian or Muslim religious affiliation that were drawn from Ekiti State Teaching Hospital Ado – Ekiti and Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital Akure, Ondo State using purposive sampling method because they met some criteria for their selection. Diagnosis of the participants cut across almost all the mental disorders, which include schizophrenia, drug addiction, depression, bipolar disorder, etc. Only

the stable patients participated in the research, which was certified through the use of Mental State Examination (MSEs).

Measures

Three instruments were used for this research, namely: the Death Anxiety Scale, the Religiosity scale, and the Meaning of Life Scale.

Death anxiety was assessed using the Death Attitude Profile–Revised (Wong, Reker, & Gesser, 1994), which comprises three subscales: Fear of Death, Death Avoidance, and Approach Acceptance of Death. The Fear of Death subscale included seven items (e.g., “I have an intense fear of death,” “Death is no doubt a grim experience”) and demonstrated good internal consistency with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.84. The Death Avoidance subscale consisted of five items (e.g., “I avoid thoughts of death at all costs,” “I always try not to think about death”) with an alpha of 0.85. The Approach Acceptance of Death subscale contained ten items (e.g., “I believe that I will be in heaven after I die,” “I look forward to life after death”) and showed excellent reliability with an alpha of 0.97. All items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Religiosity was assessed using the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Religious Orientation Scale developed by Allport and Ross (1979). This scale employs a 5-point Likert format, with responses ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The Intrinsic Religiosity subscale comprises nine items (e.g., “I try hard to carry my religion over all other dealings in life”) and demonstrated strong internal consistency with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.89. The Extrinsic Religiosity subscale includes eleven items (e.g., “A primary reason for any interest in religion is that my Church/Mosque is a congenial social activity”) and exhibited good reliability, with an alpha of 0.81. Although the validity of these scales has faced occasional criticism (Hunt & King, 1971; Karkpatrick & Hood, 1990), they remain the most widely used instruments for assessing religious orientation (Donahue, 1985) and have yet to be supplanted by any more effective measures. Moreover, both subscales demonstrate high internal consistency and effectively capture two distinct dimensions of religiosity. Participation in shared spiritual activities was measured using a single item from the Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (Hatch, et al., 1998), asking respondents to indicate how often in the past month they engaged in spiritual activities with at least one other person, on a scale ranging from 1 (“0 times”) to 5 (“more than 15 times”). Religion affiliation was measured as a dichotomous

variable. ‘Respondents who answered “none” or did not give an answer to the open-ended question “What is your religious affiliation?” were coded as having no religious affiliation.

Meaning in Life was assessed using three “pure” items from Crumbaugh and Maholick’s (1964) Purpose in Life Test (as adapted by King & Hunt, 1975). The items included statements such as, “I have discovered satisfying goals and a clear purpose in life,” “If I should die today, I would feel that my life has been worthwhile,” and “My existence often seems meaningless and without purpose.” Participants rated each item on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (not true of myself) to 5 (definitely true of myself). The negatively worded item was reverse-scored, and the mean of all three items was computed, yielding a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.65. Relapse was measured by the number of times the participants had been readmitted after being granted leave.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Ethical review board from the two hospitals which was granted. Access was permitted to the patients in the ward during psychotherapy sessions and ward rounds. Additional access was granted to the participants' files, allowing the researcher to gather more information. The instruments were provided with the help of a clinical psychologist. Since all the participants were relatively stable and educated, they could complete the instruments independently. Some instruments were administered afterward rounds, while others were given after assessments. For outpatients, the instruments were provided during their appointments with doctors. A total of one hundred questionnaires were administered, but only 86 were correctly completed, while 14 questionnaires were removed based on errors ranging from non-completion of items. The data collection for this study lasted for approximately three weeks.

Results

Correlation Analyses

The result of correlation analyses between variables are presented in Table 1. There was moderate and significant negative correlation between death avoidance and relapse [$r(85) = -.28, p = .01$]; fear of death and relapse [$r(85) = -.34, p < .0001$] while acceptance approach showed a weak and significant positive correlation with relapse [$r(85) = .22, p = .04$]. Correlation does not exist between age and relapse [$r(85) = .11, p = .33$]; neutral acceptance and relapse [$r(85) = .14, p = .19$]; escape acceptance and relapse [$r(85) = -.07, p = .55$];

extrinsic religion and relapse [$r(85) = .19, p = .08$]; intrinsic religion and relapse [$r(85) = .11, p = .30$]; meaning of life and relapse [$r(85) = .12, p = .28$].

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation scores, and correlations among study variables N=86

Variables	M (SD)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
	33.44 (8.26)	-								
1. Age	24.86 (10.23)		-							
2. Death avoidance	29.85 (8.7)			-						
3. Fear of death	26.41 (7.06)	.07	.42**							
4. Neutral acceptance	44.16 (12.14)	.21	.02	.05	-					
5. Approach acceptance	22.53 (7.63)	.03	-.34**	-.16	.17	-				
6. Escape acceptance	42.64 (7.08)	-.01	.04	.36**	.12	.23*	-			
7. Extrinsic religion	33.63 (6.31)	.10	-.09	-.04	.19	.36**	.11	-		
8. Intrinsic religion	71 (13.82)	.13	.10	-.05	.21*	.13	.07	.24*	-	
9. Meaning in life		.04	-.27*	-.26*	.13	.27*	-.08	.45**	.38**	-
10. Relapse		.11	-.28*	-.34**	.14	.22*	-.07	.19	-.11	.12

* $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed) ** $p < 0.001$ (2-tailed)

Hypothesis 1

Death anxiety will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. Binary logistic regression was performed to assess the impact of death anxiety dimensions on the likelihood that patients would relapse. The model presented in Table 2 included five independent variables—fear of death, death avoidance, neutral acceptance, approach acceptance, and escape acceptance representing the subscales of death anxiety. The overall model, which incorporated all predictors, was statistically significant, $\chi^2(5) = 18.11$, $p = .003$, demonstrating its ability to differentiate between patients who experienced relapse and those who did not. The model accounted for 19% (Cox and Snell R^2) to 29.1% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in relapse and correctly classified 80% of cases. As indicated in Table 2, only the fear of death subscale made a uniquely significant contribution to the model, with an odds ratio of 0.89. This suggests that patients with higher levels of fear of death were 0.89 times less likely to relapse compared to those with lower levels. Consequently, hypothesis one is partially supported.

Table 2: Logistic Regression Analysis testing the influence of death anxiety on relapse

Predictor	B	SE β	Wald's χ^2	Df	p	e $^\beta$ (odds ratio)	95% CI
Fear of death	-.12	.05	6.21	1	.01	.86	[.80 - .97]
Death avoidance	-.03	.03	.94	1	.33	.97	[.91 – 1.03]
Neutral acceptance	.10	.06	3.21	1	.07	1.11	[.99 – 1.24]
Approach acceptance	.02	.03	.34	1	.56	1.02	[.96 – 1.08]
Escape acceptance	-.02	.05	.17	1	.68	.98	[.89 – 1.08]
Constant	3.16	2.17	2.12	1	.15	23.48	
Overall model evaluation							
Model χ^2	18.11	p=.003					
Pseudo R^2	.29						
N =86							

Hypothesis 2

Religiosity will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. Binary logistic regression was performed to assess the influence of religiosity dimensions on the likelihood that patients would relapse.

The model shown in Table 3 included two independent variables which are intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity representing the subscales of religiosity. The overall model approached statistical significance, $\chi^2(2) = 5.53$, $p = .06$, suggesting that it was not effective in distinguishing between patients who relapsed and those who did not. Although extrinsic religiosity contributed significantly to the model, with an odds ratio of 1.09, the findings indicate that hypothesis two is not supported.

Table 3: Logistic Regression Analysis testing the influence of religiosity on relapse

Predictor	B	Se ^{β}	Wald's χ^2	Df	p	e ^{β} (odds ratio)	95% CI
Extrinsic religion	.08	.04	4.12	1	.042	1.09	[1.00 – 1.18]
Intrinsic religion	-.07	.05	2.22	1	.14	.94	[.86 – 1.02]
Constant	.08	1.98	.002	1	.97	1.09	
Overall model evaluation							
Model χ^2	5.53	p= .06					
Pseudo R	.10						
N	86						

Hypothesis 3

The meaning in life will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. Binary logistic regression was performed to assess the influence of the meaning of life on the likelihood that the patients would relapse. The model in Table 4.4 contained one independent variable, which is the meaning of life. The model is not significant, $\chi^2(1) = 1.23$, $p = .27$, indicating that the model was unable to distinguish between respondents who relapsed and

those who did not. Hence, the meaning of life does not predict relapse among psychiatric patients. Therefore, hypothesis three is not supported.

Table 4: Logistic regression analysis testing the influence of the meaning of life on relapse

Predictor	B	Se ^B	Wald	Df	p	e ^B	95% CI
			χ^2			(odds ratio)	
Meaning of life	.02	.02	1.19	1	.28	1.02	[.98 – 1.06]
Constant	-.25	1.39	.032	1	.86	.78	
Overall model evaluation							
Model χ^2	1.23	p= .27					
Pseudo R	.02						
N=86							

Hypothesis 4

Death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning of life will jointly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. Binary logistic regression was conducted to examine the impact of death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning in life on the likelihood of patient relapse. The model presented in Table 5 included death anxiety subscales (fear of death, death avoidance, neutral acceptance, approach acceptance, and escape acceptance), religiosity subscales (intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity), and meaning in life. The overall model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(8) = 26.40$, $p = .001$, indicating that it effectively distinguished between patients who relapsed and those who did not. The model accounted for 26.4% (Cox and Snell R^2) to 40.5% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in relapse and correctly classified 86% of cases.

As indicated in Table 4.5, three predictors fear of death, neutral acceptance, and intrinsic religiosity made uniquely significant contributions to the model. Neutral acceptance emerged as the strongest predictor of relapse, with an odds ratio (OR) of 1.19, suggesting that patients with higher levels of neutral acceptance were 1.19 times more likely to experience relapse compared to those with lower levels. In contrast, higher levels of fear of death (OR = 0.87) were associated with a reduced likelihood of relapse, as were higher levels of intrinsic religiosity (OR = 0.88). These findings indicate that hypothesis four is partially supported.

Table 5: Logistic regression analysis testing the influence of death anxiety, religiosity and meaning of life on relapse

Predictor	B	SE ^b	Wald's χ^2	Df	p	e ^{β} (odds ratio)	95% CI
Fear of death	-.14	.50	7.33	1	.01	.87	[.79 - .96]
Death avoidance	-.05	.03	2.20	1	.14	.95	[.89 – 1.02]
Neutral acceptance	.17	.07	5.75	1	.02	1.19	[1.03 – 1.37]
Approach acceptance	.002	.03	.004	1	.95	1.002	[.94 – 1.06]
Escape acceptance	-.04	.05	.66	1	.42	.96	[.86 – 1.06]
Extrinsic religiosity	.12	.07	3.40	1	.07	1.13	[.99 – 1.28]
Intrinsic religiosity	-.12	.06	4.09	1	.04	.88	[.78 – 1.00]
Meaning of life	-.02	.03	.57	1	.45	.98	[.93 – 1.04]
Constant	4.32	3.26	1.76	1	.19	75.19	-
Overall model evaluation							
Model χ^2	26.40	p = .001					
Pseudo R	.41						
N = 86							

Discussion

The study has been able to examine the predictive roles of religiosity, death anxiety, and meaning in Life on relapse among psychiatric patients. The study tested four hypotheses in all. Hypothesis one posited that death anxiety would significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. The study revealed that only the fear of death subscale contributed uniquely and significantly on relapse. Therefore, hypothesis one is partially supported. The study finding was similar with studies done by Wen Yh and Wen Ddyh (2010) and Adelbratt and Strang (2000) earlier reported that death anxiety contributes to significant emotional and behavioral consequences, especially in patients with end-stage illnesses. The study finding was also in line with Omolayo, Mokuolu, Balogun, Olawa, and Omole (2013) who found that insightful patients are less likely to relapse. The study finding was also in line with studies done

by (Corrigan, 2000; Hudson, Owen Trush, 2004; Valerstein, Blow, Capeland, 2004; Corrigan, 2000; Gureje, 2000; Corrigan, 2000) who found that death anxiety predict relapse.

Hypothesis two proposed that religiosity would significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. The results indicated that the model could not differentiate between patients who relapsed and those who did not, although extrinsic religiosity did make a statistically significant contribution. Consequently, hypothesis two is not supported. The study finding was not in line with Aggarwal et al. (2023) who found that spiritual well-being correlates with lower depressive and anxiety symptoms, whereas negative religious coping correlates with worse outcomes. The study finding was not in line with Malinakova et al. (2024) who demonstrated that under conditions of high sensory-processing sensitivity, religiosity/spirituality can associate with greater mental-health symptoms. The study finding was also not in line with Boateng et al. (2023) found that in some U.S. samples, higher religiosity was associated with greater utilisation of mental-health services, challenging earlier assumptions of uniform reluctance. The study finding was also similar with Antoniou and Kalogeropoulos (2024) who further revealed that for religious client's faith can serve as both resilience and barrier depending on context and community attitudes. The rationale for the study maybe that participants might see themselves as invincible to relapse, and they have already formed that cognitive picture, hence the religiosity or otherwise of the participants might not even have a direct impact on the relapse rate of participants used for the study.

Hypothesis three proposed that meaning in life would significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. The findings indicated that meaning in life was unable to differentiate between patients who relapsed and those who did not, suggesting that meaning in life does not significantly predict relapse in this population. Therefore, hypothesis three is not supported. The outcome of this result could be explained using the postulations of three leading scholars on the meaning in life as it relates to clinical psychology. Frankl (1976), Maslow (1971), and Yalom (1980) all recognized that an existential vacuum can lead to a range of psychopathological symptoms, such as alcoholism, depression, excessive sexual behavior, and thrill-seeking. Going by these description by Maddi (1991), meaninglessness of life could be seen as a psychiatric symptoms for some mental situations which was the diagnoses of participants used and since the participants used for the current study are insightful and to a certain treatment regime for quite some times and regularly attending psychotherapy sessions

(as indicated in their files) they might have been able to have a different orientation about life entirely, therefore the study might fail to find a link between it and relapse.

Hypothesis four states that death anxiety, religiosity, and meaning of life will significantly predict relapse among psychiatric patients. The study indicated that patients who had a higher level of neutral acceptance were more likely to relapse than those who had lower levels of neutral acceptance. Also, patients with higher levels of fear of death were less likely to relapse than those who had lower levels of fear of death. Additionally, patients with higher levels of intrinsic religiosity were less likely to relapse than those who had lower levels of intrinsic religiosity. Therefore, hypothesis four is partially supported.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, we concluded that fear of death subscale, neutral acceptance and intrinsic religiosity sub dimension play a significant joint role on relapse among psychiatry patients. Based on the conclusion, we recommend that clinical psychologists should develop a psychoeducation that can lower fear of death among psychiatric patients which in turn may decrease relapse. The study also recommends that religion institutions should inculcate strong values and doctrine that will make psychiatric patients remain resilient which in turn will not make them relapse.

Limitation and Suggestions for Future Studies

There are no studies without its limitations. The first limitation is the small sample used for the study which in a way may limit generalization. Future studies may increase the sample of the study in a bid for more robust generalization. Also, the use of questionnaire may tend social desirability effect which may bias finding in some way. Future studies may consider utilizing qualitative method which may give more direct insights regarding the relapse situation of psychiatry patients. Lastly, only three psychological variables were investigated in this study which give minimal insights into the relapse situation psychiatric patients. Lastly, future studies may investigate more psychosocial variables such as emotional intelligence, resilience and personality traits. These variables may give more explanation to the experience of relapse among psychiatric patients.

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